

2023 ASIAN BIODIVERSITY DATA USE GUIDE

Linking to the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals and Open Science

GBIF ASIA

GBIF CAS (Chinese Academy of Sciences) Node

March 2024

UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

In 2015, world leaders agreed to 17 goals for a better world by 2030. We recognise that eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions, including extreme poverty, is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development. All countries and all stakeholders, acting in collaborative partnership, will implement this plan. We are resolved to free the human race from the tyranny of poverty and want and to heal and secure our planet. We are determined to take the bold and transformative steps which are urgently needed to shift the world onto a sustainable and resilient path. As we embark on this collective journey, we pledge that no one will be left behind. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 169 targets which we are announcing today demonstrate the scale and ambition of this new universal Agenda.

The official website: <https://www.globalgoals.org/>

Open science

Following an inclusive, transparent and multistakeholder consultative process, the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science was adopted by the 41st session of UNESCO General Conference in November 2021. Open Science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

The official website: <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

GBIF Data Status in Asia

There are currently 126,470,316 occurrences in Asia, 4.73 % of total GBIF records
(By 12 March, 2024)

TOP 10 Countries or Areas have most occurrences in Asia

Country or area	Count
India	41,053,858
Chinese Taipei	18,072,100
China	10,162,486
Japan	7,035,414
Korea, Republic of	6,698,055
Israel	5,092,208
Thailand	4,991,657
Russian Federation	4,050,577
Malaysia	3,180,033
Indonesia	2,605,276

TOP 10 Countries or Areas contributed data in Asia

Publishing country or area	Count
India	38,687,282
Chinese Taipei	17,480,462
United States of America	9,322,147
Japan	6,551,581
China	6,532,165
Korea, Republic of	6,137,690
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	4,861,171
Israel	4,798,779
Thailand	3,781,678
Netherlands (Kingdom of the)	2,315,243

TOP 10 Data Publishers contributed data in Asia

Publisher	Count
Cornell Lab of Ornithology	77,862,862
iNaturalist.org	5,744,065
Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)	4,266,744
Taiwan Biodiversity Research Institute	4,152,752
National Museum of Nature and Science, Japan	3,925,385
MGrnify	2,239,475
National Institute of Ecology	1,916,432
Naturalis Biodiversity Center	1,557,614
National Institute of Genetics, ROIS	1,305,169
National Science Museum of Korea	1,288,626

CONTENTS

PREFACE	4
INTRO	5
THE 17 GOALS	
1 No Poverty	6
2 Zero Hunger	8
3 Good Health and Well-Being	11
4 Quality Education	13
5 Gender Equality	16
6 Clean Water and Sanitation	18
7 Affordable and Clean Energy	19
8 Decent Work and Economic Growth	20
9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	21
10 Reduced Inequalities	24
11 Sustainable Cities and Communities	26
12 Responsible Consumption and Production	29
13 Climate Action	31
14 Life below Water	34
15 Life on Land	36
16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	39
17 Partnerships for the Goals	41
INDEX OF GUIDE	43

Preface

The value of data lies in its use. As the largest biodiversity occurrence data portal, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is dedicated “to mobilize the data, skills and technologies needed to make comprehensive biodiversity information freely available for science and decisions addressing biodiversity loss and sustainable development”.

To date, GBIF has shared over 2.6 billion records and has contributed to the production of more than 20,209 journal articles. However, despite being the largest Continent on the earth, Asia has contributed only 126,506,014 occurrences, accounting for a mere 4.73 % of the total GBIF records. Various factors have hindered the sharing of biodiversity occurrence data from this region. It is imperative to engage more individuals, institutions and organizations within the region to promote contributions to biodiversity data sharing and mobilization efforts. Urgent action is needed to address this gap and ensure broader participation in this crucial endeavor.

According to the "2023-2027 GBIF Strategic Framework", GBIF will primarily focus on four key areas: science and research, policy and partnerships, community and capacity, infrastructure and data products. Currently, two significant global initiatives, namely the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Open Science, rely heavily on open data and other research activities. GBIF is poised to increase its contributions to these endeavors in the future. In fact, GBIF has been selected as one of the knowledge sharing platforms of UNESCO Open Science plan.

To advance the goal of supporting SDGs and Open Science, it's important to showcase various data uses and applications through a guide or handbook. Consequently, the teams of GBIF Asia and GBIF Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) Node have compiled 37 case studies from academic articles, categorizing them based on different SDGs, Open Science elements, and areas. I am pleased to introduce this work to all the colleagues involved in biodiversity science and conservation. I would like to take this opportunity to congratulate the authors on this achievement!

Keping MA
Head of delegation, GBIF CAS Node
Vice Chair & Secretary General, Biodiversity Committee, CAS
Professor of Institute of Botany, CAS

12 March, 2024

INTRO

The 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) represent the global aspiration for a better life and a more sustainable future. Open Science serves a way to engage diverse stakeholders and research endeavors in achieving these goals. Biodiversity stands as a crucial element for human beings, the planet and SDGs. The era of big data and artificial intelligence (AI) is upon us, and will significantly influence digital transformation and cooperation.

Presently, various large biodiversity data portals, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), have been established. However, there exist disparities in data sharing across regions. Notably, Asia, the largest continent, contributes only 4.73% of the total GBIF records. It's urgent to involve more individuals in data sharing efforts to ensure a sustainable future for our planet.

To provide exemplary guides, the team from National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences and the Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences have curated articles published in 2023 from diverse sources, such as Web of Science (WoS), Dimensions, and the GBIF literature database. These articles are annotated with classifications and tags, with 1-3 cases highlighted for each goal. Moreover, we ensure representation from the six sub-regions of Asia: East Asia, West Asia, Southeast Asia, Central Asia, South Asia and North Asia. Each case study incorporates elements of Open Science, including Open Scientific Publication(OSP), Open Research Data(ORD), Open Source Software (OSS), Open Educational Resources(OER) and Citizen Science(CS).

This guide is dedicated to researchers and students committed to the protection and management of biodiversity, as well as to policymakers seeking to understand the intersections between biodiversity and the SDGs/Open Science. It also extends to all citizens, professionals, and institutions, organizations joining in the collective challenge of addressing social and governance needs while safeguarding the planet.

On behalf of the Editorial Committee

Zheping Xu
Nodes Regional Representative Asia
Node Manager of GBIF CAS

12 March, 2024

HOW TO CITE: Zheping Xu, Tian Jiang, Maofang Luo, Xuejuan Chen(2024)2023 Asia Biodiversity Data Use Guide: Linking to the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals and Open Science.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: Base and Talent Special Project of Ministry of Science and Technology (2022XJKK1505); Library and Information Capacity Building Project of Chinese Academy of Sciences(E1290002)

1.1 DIVERSITY OF WILD EDIBLE FRUITS IN THE AGROFORESTRY AREA OF CIGALONTANG VILLAGE, TASIKMALAYA, INDONESIA

Indonesia

Challenge

Wild edible fruits are non-timber forest products that support the nutritional adequacy of communities around the forest. Scientific inventory and documentation of wild fruit plant diversity are important to reveal local resources' potential in supporting local communities food security.

Contribution

1. The interviews and fieldwork results showed that 49 species of WEF belong to 27 families . Zingiberaceae, Moraceae, Arecaceae, Melastomataceae, and Rosaceae were the top five families contributing to providing WEF for the people of Cigalontang Village.
2. The significance of the WEF inventory is to provide information on its diversity in nature before its presence declines due to deforestation and land conversion. This information is essential for the younger generation to become aware and care about the diversity of WEF around where they live so that imported fruits do not erode the existence of WEF.

Citation

Kulsum NNS, Susandarini R. 2023. Diversity of wild edible fruits in the agroforestry area of Cigalontang Village, Tasikmalaya, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas* 24: 4161-4167.
DOI: 10.13057/biodiv/d240755

1 NO POVERTY

Data Uses

Plant specimen databases including Biodiversity Heritage Library (<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/>), GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/>), World Flora Online (<http://www.worldfloraonline.org/>). Verification of valid species names was carried out in reference to Plants of the World Online (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia

Figure 1. Location of Cigalontang Village, Tasikmalaya, West Java, Indonesia

1.2 CROP WILD RELATIVES IN LEBANON: MAPPING THE DISTRIBUTION OF POACEAE AND FABACEAE PRIORITY TAXA FOR CONSERVATION PLANNING

Lebanon

Challenge

Within the context of climate change and its adverse effect on agrobiodiversity, conservation of CWRs in Lebanon is essential to prevent the loss of potentially useful genetic diversity and to facilitate their use in crop breeding.

Contribution

This study provided a foundation for further research into the conservation planning of crop wild relatives belonging to Poaceae and Fabaceae in Lebanon by identifying areas with highest taxa richness.

Citation

Sayde, E., Raggi, L., Chalak, L. et al. Crop wild relatives in Lebanon: mapping the distribution of Poaceae and Fabaceae priority taxa for conservation planning. *Genet Resour Crop Evol* 70, 2097–2113 (2023). DOI: 10.1007/s10722-023-01561-4.

Data Uses

As for CWR taxa present in Lebanon belonging to Poaceae and Fabaceae, 40 from GBIF, 42 taxa resulted from ICARDA's database, 33 from GENESYS database.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Università Degli Studi Di Perugia, Italy
2. Lebanese University, Lebanon
3. International Center for Agricultural Research in Dry Areas (ICARDA), Lebanon

Fig. 1 Distribution (top) and density (bottom) maps of cereals priority taxa belonging to *Aegilops*, *Triticum* and *Hordeum* genera. In the distribution maps, main regions hosting CWR populations are highlighted; in density maps, cell and map colours are displayed according to the "density" and "altitude" scales, respectively

Fig. 2 Distribution (top) and density (bottom) maps of legumes priority taxa belonging to *Cicer*, *Lens* and *Pisum* genera. In the distribution maps, main regions hosting CWR populations are highlighted; in density maps, cell and map colours are displayed according to the "density" and "altitude" scales, respectively

2.1 DULONG PEOPLE'S TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE OF *CARYOTA OBTUSA* (ARECACEAE): A POTENTIAL STARCH PLANT WITH EMPHASIS ON ITS STARCH PROPERTIES AND DISTRIBUTION PREDICTION

China

Challenge

The greatest global challenge is to ensure that all people have access to adequate and nutritious food. Wild edible plants, particularly those that provide substitutes for staple foods, can play a key role in enhancing food security and maintaining a balanced diet in rural communities.

Contribution

C. obtusa is a viable potential starch-producing species with high cultural importance in the Dulong community. It can make positive contributions to food security and bring income as well. In the future, it is necessary to study the breeding and cultivation of *C. obtusa*, as well as the processing and development of starch, to contribute to solving long-term hidden hunger in rural areas.

Citation

Cheng, Z., Lu, X., Hu, X. et al. Dulong People's Traditional Knowledge of *Caryota obtusa* (Arecaceae): a Potential Starch Plant with Emphasis on Its Starch Properties and Distribution Prediction. *Econ Bot* 77, 63–81 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12231-022-09565-4>

2 ZERO HUNGER

Data Uses

MaxEnt software (version 3.4.1) was downloaded from the Museum of Natural History website (<https://www.amnh.org/>). The 187 distribution data of *C. obtusa* were obtained by searching GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility, <https://www.gbif.org/>), FoC (Flora of China, <http://www.iplant.cn/foc>), PPBC (Plant Photo Bank of China, <http://ppbc.iplant.cn/>), and CVH (Chinese Virtual Herbarium, <https://www.cvh.ac.cn/>) and 25 distribution points recorded by our laboratory from August 2019 to September 2021.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Minzu University of China, China
2. Xishuangbanna Tropical Botanical Garden, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China

Fig. 4. A. Distribution of *C. obtusa* in Asia. B. Potential geographical distribution of *C. obtusa* under the current climate.

2.2 SMART FARMING: MODELING DISTRIBUTION OF *XANTHOMONAS CAMPESTRIS* PV. *ORYZAE* AS A LEAF BLIGHT-CAUSING BACTERIA IN RICE PLANTS.

Indonesia

Challenge

Among all crop inputs, pesticide uses initially aimed to control various pests and disease carriers. However, the unrestricted use of these chemicals is proven to create more problems when they harm the environment and are lethal to pests and non-target species.

Contribution

The bacteria occurrences positively correlate with several climatic variables and spread throughout the archipelago presented into five classes. Main islands such as Java, Bali, and Sumatra share areas with the highest suitability values. While Kalimantan and Sulawesi only share small areas with high suitability area. Papua has a less suitable location for the bacteria to spread. Rice cultivation is inseparable from the threat of pests and diseases. It can cause losses in the form of decreased production to crop failure. Therefore, The Species Distribution Model needed to identify areas where the vector is likely to occur. This way, mitigation or even prevention efforts could be made effectively.

Citation

M H Saputra et al 2023 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 1133 012026. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/1133/1/012026.

Data Uses

The occurrences data was extracted from the GBIF. the climate data was obtained from the Worldclim data set. The Species Distribution Model used the Maximum entropy method available on the Ecocommons website.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

National Research and Innovation Agency Republic of Indonesia (BRIN), Indonesia

Figure 1. The prediction of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* distribution model

Figure 4. The limits factors of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* to the climatic variables

2.3 ETHNOBOTANY OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN THE DAYAK LINOH TRIBE IN SINTANG DISTRICT, INDONESIA

Indonesia

Challenge

The Linoh Dayak people have long used medicinal plants to deal with health problems in their community. However, along with the advancement of science, the influx of foreign cultures and the degradation of nature and the environment, traditional knowledge about medicinal plants is only owned by the older generation, and the transmission of information is limited by word of mouth and not well documented.

Contribution

This study revealed that people in the Linoh Dayak community utilized various plant organs as medicinal ingredients, i.e., tendrils (stolon), root, tuber, tuber, rhizome, stem, leaf, flower, fruit, fruit peel, and seed.

This research concluded that the Dayak Linoh people in Nobal Village, Sungai Tebelian Subdistrict, still have knowledge regarding the use of plants as traditional medicine. Knowledge of traditional medicines in the Dayak Linoh tribe can be used for developing modern medicine.

Citation

Julung H, Supiandi MI, Ege B, Zubaidah S, Mahanal S. 2023. Ethnobotany of medicinal plants in the Dayak Linoh Tribe in Sintang District, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas* 24: 767-775. DOI: 10.13057/biodiv/d240212.

2 ZERO HUNGER

Data Uses

The scientific names of medicinal plants were obtained by consulting online databases, specifically the International Plant Names Index (IPNI) available at ipni.org, Plants of the World Online at powo.science.kew.org, The Plant List at theplantlist.org, and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility at gbif.org.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang, Indonesia.
2. Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia.

Figure 1. Research area in Nobal Village, Sungai Tebelian Subdistrict, Sintang District, West Kalimantan, Indonesia

3.1 POTENTIAL INDIVIDUAL AND INTERACTIVE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE AND LAND-COVER CHANGES ON BATS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR CONSERVATION PLANNING: A CASE STUDY IN VIETNAM

Vietnam

Challenge

Climate and land-cover changes are among major threats to biodiversity. However, the interactive effects of the two threats are often overlooked in conservation planning.

Contribution

These results underscore the urgent need to incorporate both climate and land-cover changes, as well as their interactions, into conservation planning for bats in Vietnam and biodiversity in general. The species-specific and spatially-explicit information regarding the impacts of the two threats can guide conservation actions, allowing us to target more manageable and less uncertain threats, as well as prioritize the protection of more vulnerable species.

Citation

Tuan, L.Q., Thong, V.D., Son, N.T. et al. Potential individual and interactive effects of climate and land-cover changes on bats and implications for conservation planning: a case study in Vietnam. *Biodivers Conserv* 32, 4481–4508 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-023-02709-5>

Data Uses

Occurrence records of the species from the GBIF using the `rgbif` package in R. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.28jn5y>.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. National Taiwan Normal University
2. Academia Sinica
3. Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology (VAST), Vietnam
4. Institute of Tropical Biology, Vietnam
5. Vietnam National University, Vietnam
6. Hungarian Natural History Museum, Hungary
7. University of Pécs, Hungary

Fig. 1 Current land cover and predicted current and future species richness across Vietnam. The boundaries and the names of eight regions in Vietnam are shown in (a). The current bat species richness was derived from the predictions of the species distribution models for 81 species in Vietnam. The locations of current protected areas shown in (b) are from the World Database on Protected Areas (categories I to VI; UNEP-WCMC and IUCN 2023). The predicted species richness in the 2050s under the moderate emission scenario shown in (c) was the median of the predictions under 10 GCMS' projections

3.2 MAPPING POTENTIAL REGIONS OF HUMAN INTERACTION WITH ACUMINATE HORSESHOE BATS (*RHINOLOPHUS ACUMINATUS*) IN THAILAND

Thailand

Challenge

Bats are reservoirs for various pathogens, including SARS-like coronaviruses (CoVs). Understanding the distribution of bat species is crucial to identifying areas where viral spillover from bats to other animals or humans might occur.

Contribution

This study performed species distribution modeling to predict suitable habitats within Thailand under current and predicted future climate conditions for *Rhinolophus acuminatus*. Their findings will significantly aid future risk surveillance efforts and enhance the effectiveness of monitoring and managing emerging diseases within the country and in contiguous regions.

Citation

Sirichan, N.; Chaiyes, A.; Sánchez, C.A.; Wacharapluesadee, S.; Srikulnath, K.; Duengkae, P. Mapping Potential Regions of Human Interaction with Acuminate Horseshoe Bats (*Rhinolophus acuminatus*) in Thailand. *Diversity* 2023, 15, 1216. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15121216>

Data Uses

GBIF <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/download/0001775-230918134249559>

Cave-Dwelling Bats of Thailand (1 record), *Wildlife Yearbook* by the Department of National Parks, Wildlife and Plant Conservation (11 records), *Horseshoe Bats of the World* (Chiroptera: Rhinolophidae) (4 records)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Kasetsart University, Thailand
2. Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand
3. EcoHealth Alliance, USA
4. King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital, Thailand
5. Kasetsart University, Thailand

Figure 3. The IUCN Red List distribution of *Rhinolophus acuminatus* (yellow) is overlaid on a map of Thailand and surrounding countries. The turquoise dots denote *R. acuminatus* occurrence locations sourced from the literature and used in model construction.

Figure 4. Potential habitat suitability for *Rhinolophus acuminatus* in Thailand under (a) present conditions and future climate scenarios for (b) 2050 and (c) 2070.

4.1 IDENTIFYING HIGH SNAKEBITE RISK AREA UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE FOR COMMUNITY EDUCATION AND ANTIVENOM DISTRIBUTION

Iran

Challenge

Snakebite is one of the largest risks from wildlife, however little is known about venomous snake distribution, spatial variation in snakebite risk, potential changes in snakebite risk pattern due to climate change, and vulnerable human population. As a consequence, management and prevention of snakebite is hampered by this lack of information.

Contribution

This paper identified areas with high snakebite risk in Iran and showed that snakebite risk will increase in some parts of the country. They underline that in order to improve snakebite management, areas which were identified with high snakebite risk in Iran need to be prioritized for the distribution of antivenom medication and awareness rising programs among vulnerable human population.

Citation

Yousefi, M., Yousefkhani, S.H., Grünig, M. et al. Identifying high snakebite risk area under climate change for community education and antivenom distribution. *Sci Rep* 13, 8191 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-35314-1>

Data Uses

GBIF, VertNet

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software, Open Educational resources, Citizen Science

Affiliations

1. Damghan University, Iran
2. Museum Koenig, Germany
3. Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany
4. University of Tehran, Iran
5. Graduate University of Advanced Technology, Iran
6. INRIA Startup Studio, France
7. Hakim Sabzevari University, Iran

Figure 1. Snakebite risk maps of the 10 species (*Echis carinatus* (a), *Gloydius halyz* (b), *Macrovipera lebetina* (c), *Montivipera latifii* (d), *Montivipera raddei* (e), *Naja oxiana* (f), *Pseudocerastes persicus* (g), *Pseudocerastes urarachnoides* (h), *Vipera erivanensis* (i), *Walterinnesia aegyptia* (j)) under current and future (year 2071–2100 SSP585) climatic. Maps were generated using QGIS 3.4.1 (<https://www.qgis.org>).

4.2 CONSERVING POTENTIAL AND ENDANGERED SPECIES OF *PERICOPSIS MOONIANA* THWAITES IN INDONESIA

Indonesia

Challenge

Kayu kuku (*Pericopsis mooniana* Thwaites) is considered a fancy wood used for sawn timber, veneer, plywood, carving, and furniture. The high demand for wood caused excessive logging and threatened its sustainability. In addition, planting *P. mooniana* has presented several challenges, including seedling production, viability and germination rate, nursery technology, and silviculture techniques. Based on The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species, *P. mooniana* is categorized as Vulnerable (A1cd). This conservation status has raised issues regarding its biodiversity, conservation, and sustainability in the near future.

Contribution

This paper aims to review the conservation of potential and endangered species of *P. mooniana* and highlight some efforts for its species conservation and sustainable use in Indonesia.

Citation

Kinho, J.; Suhartati; Husna; Tuheteru, F.D.; Arini, D.I.D.; Lawasi, M.A.; Ura', R.; Prayudyaningsih, R.; Yulianti; Subarudi; et al. Conserving Potential and Endangered Species of *Pericopsis mooniana* Thwaites in Indonesia. *Forests* 2023, 14, 437. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14020437>

Data Uses

Hills, R. *Pericopsis elata*. Available online: <https://www.gbif.org/species/176802781>; Asian Regional Workshop. *Pericopsis mooniana*. Available online: <https://www.gbif.org/species/176802779>

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open Educational resources

Affiliations

1. National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia
2. Halu Oleo University, Indonesia

Figure 3. Distribution map of *P. mooniana* in Indonesia.

Figure 5. Visualization of growth performance of *P. mooniana* with and without mycorrhizal in a post-nickel field at 12 months (A) and a post-gold mine at four months after planting (B) (Photo: F.D. Tuheteru and Husna, 2022).

4.3 STATUS OF ORNITHOLOGICAL WORKS FROM THE STATE OF CHHATTISGARH, INDIA, AND CONSERVATION IMPLICATIONS: A REVIEW

India

Challenge

This urbanizing world necessitates our conservation efforts to protect vulnerable species from being pushed to extinction. To conserve the amazing winged creatures, detailed knowledge and understanding of ornithology are imperative.

Contribution

Developing countries lose biodiversity due to rapid urbanization and heavy human pressure. Conserving the species in protected areas is not enough to arrest their population decline. Chhattisgarh needs landscape-level conservation to safeguard species, habitats, and ecosystems beyond protected areas. Nature education and awareness initiatives can help local populations protect biodiversity.

Citation

Kinho, J.; Suhartati; Husna; Tuheteru, F.D.; Arini, D.I.D.; Lawasi, M.A.; Ura', R.; Prayudyarningsih, R.; Yulianti; Subarudi; et al. Conserving Potential and Endangered Species of *Pericopsis mooniana* Thwaites in Indonesia. *Forests* 2023, 14, 437. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14020437>

Data Uses

GBIF, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Biodiversity Heritage Library, Reports, Shodhganga, IUCN Red List

Open Sciences

Open research data, Open Educational resources, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Salim Ali Centre for Ornithology and Natural History, India
2. South India Centre of Wildlife Institute of India, India
3. Environmental Sciences, Department of Chemistry and BBRC, India
4. State Coordinator IBCN, India

Fig. 1. Studied locations of Chhattisgarh state.

5.1 ETHNOBOTANY OF FOOD PLANTS USED BY MINANGKABAU COMMUNITY IN LIMA PULUH KOTA DISTRICT, WEST SUMATRA, INDONESIA

Indonesia

Challenge

The Minangkabau tribe is well known for its culture and cuisine, but documents on their knowledge and wisdom in the utilization of food plants are still limited.

Contribution

This study aims to inventory plant species used for food by Minangkabau community, assess their importance and economic value, and analyze the important landscapes where the food plants are obtained. Information from this study can support food diversification to achieve food security based on the local knowledge on the diversity of food plant species and potential landraces in Minangkabau community.

Citation

Agesti ARA, Ariyanti NS, Chikmawati T, Purwanto Y. 2023. Ethnobotany of food plants used by Minangkabau Community in Lima Puluh Kota District, West Sumatra, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas* 24: 2756-2767. DOI: 10.13057/biodiv/d240529

5 GENDER EQUALITY

Data Uses

The scientific names were verified by referring to the GBIF

Plant of the World (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Institut Pertanian Bogor, Indonesia
2. National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia

Figure 1. Map of the study sites at six villages in Lima Puluh Kota District, West Sumatra Province, Indonesia

5.2 SMOKE AND MIRRORS: THE GLOBAL TRADE IN FERN (*LYGODIUM CIRCINNATUM*) FIBER BASKETRY

Indonesia

Challenge

Why is there such taxonomic confusion about the weaving materials from *L. circinnatum* fern stems, which in global trade are variously called “ata,” “grass,” “rattan,” or “reed” baskets?

How did a small village in East Bali, Indonesia, that traditionally used *L. circinnatum* fiber to weave just four types of baskets become a global hub for fine basketry design and trade in an incredible diversity (>1000 basket types)?

How have basket producers in Bali responded to the local over-exploitation of wild *L. circinnatum* fern stems? Is it possible to quantify the quantity and value of exports of *L. circinnatum* baskets?

Contribution

Clarify confusion about *Lygodium circinnatum* fern fiber used in Bali, Indonesia, to weave basketry for international export, variously called “grass,” “rattan,” “reed,” “vine,” or “ata”.

Explain how since the 1970s, entrepreneurial “champions” in Bali and Lombok have transformed a small, informal sector activity into the world’s largest fern fiber basketry trade.

Document all stages of the *L. circinnatum* supply chain from wild fern harvest to retail outlets in Asia, Europe, and North America.

Citation

Cunningham, A.B., Brinckmann, J.A. Smoke and Mirrors: The Global Trade in Fern (*Lygodium circinnatum*) Fiber Basketry. *Econ Bot* 77, 243–266 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12231-023-09576-9>

Data Uses

The distribution of *L. circinnatum* on these islands is based on redrawn location data from the GBIF Secretariat

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Murdoch University, Australia
2. University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa
3. Traditional Medicinals, USA

Fig. 1. Trade route map. The main trade routes of *pini*, the sailing vessels typical of inter-island trade in Indonesia, in relation to the occurrence of *L. circinnatum* and trade in bundles of wild harvested stems to the raw materials trade hub (Lombok) and finished basketry marketing hub in East Bali. The distribution of *L. circinnatum* on these islands is based on redrawn location data from the GBIF Secretariat (2021).

Fig. 2. Botanical raw materials. A Large bundles (called “gabung”) of *L. circinnatum* stems imported into Bali from Borneo (via Lombok) in the warehouse of a basket entrepreneur. B Detail showing split and whole stems. C *Lygodium circinnatum* stems of different heights from different sources (Km, Kalimantan; S, Sumbawa; Fl, Flores). D Detail of *L. circinnatum* stems showing dark stem bases pulled from the rhizome rather than being selectively cut. E Detail showing how the dark stem bases are used in a decorative weave.

7.1 BIOTECHNOLOGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN BAMBOO PLANTS

China, India

Challenge

Seed propagation is ineffective for bamboo due to low seed viability, while vegetative propagation is limited to small-scale production. Genetic transformation of bamboo species remains limited, although the bamboo genome is now better understood and genetic improvement is possible.

Contribution

This review discusses protocols for in vitro propagation, in vitro flowering, synthetic seed production, and transgenic techniques used to improve bamboo. This review will provide researchers with a comprehensive overview and better understanding of bamboo biotechnology for better utilization and adaptation as a sustainable bioresource.

Citation

Ahmad, Z., Teixeira da Silva, J.A., Shahzad, A. et al. Biotechnological interventions in bamboo plants. *Plant Cell Tiss Organ Cult* 153, 459–487 (2023). DOI: 10.1007/s11240-023-02490-x

Data Uses

The worldwide distribution of an important bamboo species, *Phyllostachys edulis* (sources: <https://www.gbif.org/species/5290168>; accessed on 2 March 2023)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Nanjing Forestry University, China
2. Aligarh Muslim University, India

Fig. 1 shows the worldwide distribution of an important bamboo species, *Phyllostachys edulis* (sources: <https://www.gbif.org/species/5290168>; accessed on 2 March 2023)

Fig. 3 Bamboo mature plant. A *Dendrocalamus farinosus*; B *Gaolius angustifolia*. PC: Prof. Yulong Ding

Fig. 4 Bamboo mature plant. A *Phyllostachys edulis*. B *Dendrocalamus brandisii*. C *Chimonobambusa utilis*. D *Phyllostachys violascens*. PC: Prof. Yulong Ding

8.1 PROGRESS ON GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION, DRIVING FACTORS AND ECOLOGICAL FUNCTIONS OF NEPALESE ALDER

China, India

Challenge

At present, research on the correlation between alder and environmental factors mainly focused on the effects of nitrogen- and phosphorus-addition treatments on the growth of alder seedlings in Nepal, whereas research concentrating on the relationships between alder and hydrothermal factors such as temperature and precipitation is still lacking on a large scale. In addition, *Frankia* attached to the roots of Nepalese alder are closely related to the nitrogen fixation ability of the tree itself, and as an actinomycete in microorganisms, its activity is also affected by environmental factors.

Contribution

Nepalese alder could form symbiotic nodules with *Frankia*, which plays an important role in improving soil physical and chemical properties and facilitating vegetation secondary succession. Overall, the present review provides a reference for further studies on ecological adaptability and sustainable utilization of Nepalese alder under climate change, and also for regional ecosystem service, forestry production practice, and vegetation restoration.

Citation

Xia, C.; Zhao, W.; Wang, J.; Sun, J.; Cui, G.; Zhang, L. Progress on Geographical Distribution, Driving Factors and Ecological Functions of Nepalese Alder. *Diversity* 2023, 15, 59. DOI: 10.3390/d15010059.

Data Uses

GBIF, <https://www.gbif.org>, 184 sites, accessed on 30 September 2022
Flora of China, iPlant

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Institute of Tibetan Plateau Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
2. Institute of Tibetan Plateau Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
3. Chengdu Institute of Biology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
4. Tibet Autonomous Region Institute of Science and Technology Information, China
5. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China

Figure 1. Community structure and organ characters of Nepalese alder (Motuo, Tibet).

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of Nepalese alder based on information from specimen and literature.

9.1 TOWARDS A BIONIC IOT: ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING USING SMARTPHONE INTERROGATED PLANT SENSORS

Asia

Challenge

Using an Internet connected smartphone combined with a plant sensor allows multiple measurements at multiple locations together in real-time, potentially enabling tracking of parameter change anywhere where plants are present or introduced. This hybrid integration of widely distributed living organic systems with the Internet marks the beginning of a new bionic Internet-of-things (b-IoT).

Contribution

The totality of the integrated plant-Internet system marks a first step towards a b-IoT, a crucial technology development that can directly monitor environmental impact through several causes, including natural and human-induced impact. It can potentially expand the scope of tools in the assessment of climate change more broadly whilst simultaneously enhancing human health and wellbeing.

Citation

Guo Y, Canning J, Chaczko Z (2023) Towards a bionic IoT: Environmental monitoring using smartphone interrogated plant sensors. PLoS ONE 18(2): e0265856. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265856>

Data Uses

Distribution of *Aucuba japonica* throughout the world mapping the potential coverage of a natural sensor network. The data was updated on 29/12/2021 by GBIF.ORG .

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265856.g001>

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. University of New South Wales, Australia
2. Laseire Pty Ltd, Australia
3. University of Social Sciences & Humanities, Poland

Fig 8. Image of *Aucuba japonica*: (a) plants sheltering under a tree away from a busy street and (b): plants next to a busy street. A striking difference is observed in yellow coloration and general plant vigor related to their local environment. The plants are exposed to varying conditions, including particulate matter released from vehicle exhaust, sun, wind, and rain.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265856.g008>

9.2 REDUCING GLOBAL LAND-USE PRESSURES WITH SEAWEED FARMING

Indonesia

Challenge

Agricultural expansion to meet humanity's growing needs for food and materials is a leading driver of land-use change, exacerbating climate change and biodiversity loss. Seaweed biomass farmed in the ocean could help reduce demand for terrestrial crops and reduce agricultural greenhouse gas emissions by providing a substitute or supplement for food, animal feed and biofuels.

Contribution

They model the global expansion potential of seaweed farming and explore how increased seaweed utilization under five different scenarios that consider dietary, livestock feed and fuel production seaweed usage may affect the environmental footprint of agriculture. For each scenario, they estimate the change in environmental impacts on land from increased seaweed adoption and map plausible marine farming expansion on the basis of 34 commercially important seaweed species.

Citation

Spillias, S., Valin, H., Batka, M. et al. Reducing global land-use pressures with seaweed farming. *Nat Sustain* 6, 380–390 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01043-y>

Data Uses

GBIF.org occurrence download, September 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.bd74c9>). GBIF.org occurrence download, September 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.khbhnz>). GBIF.org occurrence download, September 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.gwsja7>).

Macroalgal Herbarium Portal Collections; Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS); Atlas of Living Australia occurrence

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. The University of Queensland, Australia.
2. International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria.
3. St Lucia, Queensland, Australia.
4. University of Tasmania, Australia.

Extended Data Fig. 2 | Global potential for seaweed farming. **A.** The global potential for seaweed farming, shown here in dark green, represents an overlay of all suitable cells for seaweed farming, based on species distribution models from 34 commercially important species and constrained by depth, distance

to the nearest port, shipping traffic, mean wave energy, the presence of marine protected areas and limiting potential to areas where each species is likely to naturally occur. **B.** The amount of suitable space per GLBIOM region. NB: regions that contribute less than 1% of the total global potential are omitted.

10.1 THE COLONIAL LEGACY OF HERBARIA

Asia

Challenge

Herbarium collections shape our understanding of Earth's flora and are crucial for addressing global change issues. Their formation, however, is not free from sociopolitical issues of immediate relevance. Despite increasing efforts addressing issues of representation and colonialism in natural history collections, herbaria have received comparatively less attention. While it has been noted that the majority of plant specimens are housed in the Global North, the extent and magnitude of this disparity have not been quantified.

Contribution

We find an inverse relationship between where plant diversity exists in nature and where it is housed in herbaria. Such disparities persist across physical and digital realms despite overt colonialism ending over half a century ago. We emphasize the need for acknowledging the colonial history of herbarium collections and implementing a more equitable global paradigm for their collection, curation and use.

Citation

Park, D.S., Feng, X., Akiyama, S. et al. The colonial legacy of herbaria. *Nat Hum Behav* 7, 1059–1068 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-023-01616-7>

10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES

Data Uses

Plant specimen data (kingdom, Plantae; basis of record, preserved specimen) from GBIF on 23 April 2021 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.nt5wvx>).

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Purdue University, USA.
2. Florida State University, USA
3. Masaryk University, Czech Republic.
5. Institute of Environmental Sciences, Kazan
6. Federal University, Russia

Fig. 11 The past movement of plant specimens across the globe based on records from GBIF. **a**, The top tenth percentile of intercontinental connections between countries where specimens have been collected and where they are currently housed regardless of collection date. The widths of the arrows are proportionate to the number of specimens dislocated and are coloured by destination continent. Collections that remained in the country of collection are not depicted. **b, c**, The intercontinental dislocation of specimens before (b) and after (c) the end of overt colonialism post World War II (date 1945). The arrows are coloured by the continent of origin. The numbers on the outer ring indicate numbers of specimens collected from (lower half) or stored in (upper half) each continent and are in multiples of 100,000. The colours on the outer ring represent different continents. Political boundaries in panel a are based on GADM.

10.2 UNEVENLY DISTRIBUTED BIOLOGICAL INVASION COSTS AMONG ORIGIN AND RECIPIENT REGIONS

Asia

Challenge

Globalization challenges sustainability by intensifying the ecological and economic impacts of biological invasions. These impacts may be unevenly distributed worldwide, with costs disproportionately incurred by a few regions.

Contribution

We identify economic cost distributions of invasions among origin and recipient countries and continents, and determine socio-economic and biodiversity-related predictors of cost dynamics.

Citation

Hudgins, E.J., Cuthbert, R.N., Haubrock, P.J. et al. Unevenly distributed biological invasion costs among origin and recipient regions. *Nat Sustain* 6, 1113–1124 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01124-6>

Data Uses

Our script searched using the species names as entered within InvaCost (harmonized using the GBIF.org Backbone Taxonomy40). Finally, we checked for matching entries in GBIF (a global database of all types of species distribution) tagged as 'Native' at the country level within the 'occ_search' function of the rgbif package v.3.6.0

Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI) Invasive Species Compendium (ISC, www.cabi.org/isc), the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Global Invasive Species Database (GISD, <http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Carleton University, Canada.
2. Queen's University, UK.
3. Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum Frankfurt, Germany.
4. University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Czech Republic.
5. Gulf University for Science and Technology, Kuwait

Fig. 1 | Continental distribution of studies, costs and IAS sent and received. (a) Number of studies from each recipient continent published in InvaCost and received in our filtered dataset. (b–d) Number of IAS associated with reported costs (b), reported monetary cost (c) and average reported cost per publication (d) associated with continent pairs, for IAS sent and received by each continent. Costs are in 2017 USD millions. Percentages in b and c correspond to the share of the total per region. Credit: base map created with Wikimedia Commons (public domain).

11.1 HUMAN ACTIVITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE ACCELERATE THE EXTINCTION RISK TO NON-HUMAN PRIMATES IN CHINA

China

Challenge

Human activity and climate change affect biodiversity and cause species range shifts, contractions, and expansions. Globally, human activities and climate change have emerged as persistent threats to biodiversity, leading to approximately 68% of the ~522 primate species being threatened with extinction.

Contribution

In summary, our study found that primates in China will continue to be severely impacted by human activity and future climate change. These impacts are projected to have a considerable effect on the extent and location of species' geographical ranges and the availability of suitable habitat. Thus, to prevent large-scale declines in primate richness, it is crucial that China, the US, EU, and other industrial countries dramatically and immediately lower CO₂ emissions and that China expand PAs in regions and habitats with wild primate populations.

Citation

Li, W.-B., Teng, Y., Zhang, M.-Y., et al (2024). Human activity and climate change accelerate the extinction risk to non-human primates in China. *Global Change Biology*, 30, e17114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17114>

Data Uses

GBIF, the Catalogue of life China 2022 annual checklist (<http://sp2000.org.cn/>), the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (<https://www.iucnredlist.org/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
2. Anhui University, China
3. International Collaborative Research Center for Huangshan Biodiversity, China
4. Tibetan Macaque Behavioral Ecology, China
5. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
6. Hefei Normal University, China
7. University of Illinois, USA
8. Dali University, China

FIGURE 1 Current highly suitable, moderately suitable, poorly suitable, and unsuitable habitat distributions of 26 primate species in China. (a) Current potential distribution under the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI); (b) current potential distribution under protected area (PA); (c) current potential distribution under gross domestic product (GDP); (d) current highly suitable, moderately suitable, poorly suitable, and unsuitable habitats, as well as the total distribution area under different environment variables. Map lines delineate study areas and do not necessarily depict accepted national boundaries.

11.2 EVALUATING THE URBAN-RURAL DIFFERENCES IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AFFECTING AMPHIBIAN ROADKILL

China

Challenge

Roads have major impacts on wildlife, and the most direct negative effect is through deadly collisions with vehicles, i.e., roadkill. Amphibians are the most frequently road-killed animal group. Due to the significant differences between urban and rural environments, the potential urban-rural differences in factors driving amphibian roadkill risks should be incorporated into the planning of mitigation measures.

Contribution

The method and outputs illustrated in this study can be useful tools to better understand amphibian road mortality in urban and rural environments and to inform mitigation assessment and conservation planning.

Citation

Zhao, J.; Yu, W.; He, K.; Zhao, K.; Zhou, C.; Wright, J.A.; Li, F. Evaluating the Urban-Rural Differences in the Environmental Factors Affecting Amphibian Roadkill. *Sustainability* 2023, 15, 6051. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15076051>

Data Uses

Data on amphibian roadkill locations were obtained from the Taiwan Roadkill Observation Network (TaiRON) database via GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/>; accessed on 1 May 2021). In this study, the TaiRON dataset obtained from the GBIF contained a total of 46,416 observations with a temporal coverage of 2011–2017.

WorldClim database (<http://www.worldclim.org/>; accessed on 23 May 2021)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Shanghai Institute of Technology, China
2. Center for Urban Road Ecological Engineering and Technology of Shanghai Municipality, China
3. University of Southampton, UK

Figure 1. Map showing the urban-rural areas of Taiwan island overlaying with the locations of obtained amphibian roadkill observations.

11.3 ARE THE SAME FACTORS DETERMINING BIODIVERSITY IN CITIES ACROSS DIFFERENT REGIONS? COMPARING DRIVERS OF URBAN BIRD RICHNESS PATTERNS IN SOUTHERN ASIA VS. WESTERN EUROPE

Southern Asia and Western Europe

Challenge

According to the prevailing urban ecological understanding, bird species richness declines in highly urban areas due to the increasing extent of built-up areas, and the deminishing proportions of green areas. However, this hypothesis primarily stems from studies conducted in cities located in the Global North, with limited exploration in the Global South.

Contribution

Our research findings indicate that the decline in bird richness is strongly correlated with high imperviousness, particularly in regions experiencing rapid urbanization. Effective urban planning that incorporates green spaces throughout cities is crucial in Southern Asia, as it is in Western Europe, to benefit both people and biodiversity.

Citation

Sultana, M., Corlatti, L. & Storch, I. Are the same factors determining biodiversity in cities across different regions? Comparing drivers of urban bird richness patterns in Southern Asia vs. Western Europe. *Urban Ecosyst* 26, 1545–1557 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-023-01404-1>

Data Uses

We collected readily available digital bird observation records from GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility; gbif.org) spanning the last 2 decades (2000–2020) in several cities across Southern Asia (GBIF 2020a) and Western Europe (GBIF 2020b, 2021).

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

University of Freiburg, Germany

Fig. 1 The map shows location of selected cities in Southern Asia (A) and Western Europe (B) considered to investigate driving factors of bird species richness along different gradients of urbanisation

12.1 SPECIES AVAILABILITY AND SOCIO-ECONOMICS DRIVE PROSECUTIONS FOR REGIONAL MAMMAL AND BIRD POACHING ACROSS CHINA, 2014–2020

China

Challenge

The illegal poaching of vertebrate species, whether for subsistence or economic trade, poses a significant global threat to biodiversity, ecosystem functionality and public health. China has implemented substantial wildlife protection measures in recent decades, leading to the recovery of various flagship species, threatened by poaching, from the brink of extinction. However, to achieve effective conservation interventions and avoid oversimplified narratives, it is essential to gain a deeper understanding of the complex processes driving poaching across China.

Contribution

Based on our findings, we recommend that prevention and control measures should be specifically targeted to consider these prefectural and biodiversity-base factors influencing the poaching of various taxa. In prefectures with richer biodiversity, initiatives should focus on providing alternative livelihoods to subsistence hunting of mammals, coupled with zoning regulations to prevent residential development in biodiverse areas. In wealthier prefectures, stricter policing and enforcement of bird trading would be most effective. This targeted action, aimed at guiding both development and wildlife protection efforts in China and similarly biodiverse countries, is essential to both reduce dependencies on poaching and demand from more affluent consumers.

Citation

Zi-Xuan Zhao, Mei-Ling Shao, Chris Newman, et al. Species availability and socio-economics drive prosecutions for regional mammal and bird poaching across China, 2014–2020, *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 2023,46(e02583). ISSN 2351-9894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02583>.

Data Uses

1440,460 occurrence records for bird species and 1655 occurrences for mammal species from GBIF National Bureau of Statistics of China (see <http://www.stats.gov.cn/english/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. China West Normal University, China
2. University of Oxford, UK
3. China West Normal University, China

Fig. 1. The geographical distribution of where poaching occurred (dots) and the number of mammal (A) and bird (B) species poached (dot size) in mainland China. The base map was created from the Natural Earth Dataset (<http://www.naturalearthdata.com/>).

12.2 ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION OF THREATENED MEDICINAL PLANTS IN THE TRANS-HIMALAYAN REGION OF NANDA DEVI BIOSPHERE RESERVE, WESTERN HIMALAYA

India

Challenge

The Trans-Himalayan region harbors a wealth of valuable medicinal plants renowned for their therapeutic properties. However, factors such as overgrazing, excessive harvesting, habitat destruction, and climate change have led to a decline in their wild populations. The excessive collection of these plants for medicine, local consumption and illegal trade has resulted in detrimental consequences. This uncontrolled exploitation endangers their wild population, regeneration, and survival.

Contribution

To address these challenges, the study recommends preparing micro-plans, assessing available growing stock, and implementing sustainable management practices to conserve the dwindling populations. The study highlights the urgent need for conservation efforts in the Trans-Himalayan region.

Citation

Arun Pratap Mishra, Amit Kumar, Shiv Narayan Yadav, Ecology and conservation of threatened medicinal plants in the Trans-Himalayan region of Nanda Devi Biosphere Reserve, Western Himalaya, *Trees, Forests and People*, 2023, 14(100451), ISSN 2666-7193, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tfp.2023.100451>.

Data Uses

the Human Footprint (HFP) layer, accessible at <http://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/wildareas/>. We also incorporated the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) layer, available at <https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mod09a1v061/>

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

Wildlife Institute of India, India

Fig. 1. Map showing Niti valley in the Nanda Devi Biosphere Reserve, Western Himalaya.

Fig. 3. Habitat suitability of high value and threatened medicinal plants in Niti Valley. (A) *Arnebia benthamii*, (B) *Dactylorhiza hatagiroi*, (C) *Pterorhiza kurroo*, (D) *Saussurea obtusata* and (E) *Sinopodophyllum hexandrum*.

13.1 DISTRIBUTION CHANGE AND PROTECTED AREA PLANNING OF *TILIA AMURENSIS* IN CHINA: A STUDY OF INTEGRATING THE CLIMATE CHANGE AND PRESENT HABITAT LANDSCAPE PATTERN

China, India

Challenge

Tilia amurensis, classified as a national class II endangered plant in China, plays an essential role in maintaining the stability of regional forest communities and serves as an essential economic tree species in Northeast Asia. With the growing concern over the impact of rapid climate change on the distribution and adaptability of plant populations in recent years, there remains a knowledge gap in our understanding the future distribution changes of this important species.

Contribution

In this study, they used an ensemble species distribution model to simulate the distribution of *T. amurensis* in China under different climate scenarios. The findings offer valuable insights that can aid in effective protection and sustainable utilization of *T. amurensis* under climate change.

Citation

Bingrui Chen, Hui Zou, Boyan Zhang, et al. Distribution change and protected area planning of *Tilia amurensis* in China: A study of integrating the climate change and present habitat landscape pattern, *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 2023(43), e02438, ISSN 2351-9894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02438>.

Data Uses

Occurrence data for *T. amurensis* were compiled from the GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org>) the National Specimen Information Infrastructure (<http://www.nsii.org.cn>), the Chinese Virtual Herbarium (<https://www.cvh.ac.cn>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

Harbin normal university, China

Fig. 1. Distribution map of *T. amurensis* occurrence data and individual picture: (a) Occurrence data of *T. amurensis*; (b) Individuals of *T. amurensis*; (c) Flowers of *T. amurensis*.

Fig. 2. (a): Current suitable area of *T. amurensis* in China; (b): Vegetation type and dry and wet areas in China (full names of regions can be found in Table S8); (c): Spatial distribution pattern change of forest landscape fragmentation in different years; (d): Land use area in each year; (e): Proportion of fragmentation grade of forest landscape area percentage from 1980 to 2020.

13.2 POTENTIAL DISTRIBUTION OF TWO ECONOMIC LAYER SPECIES-*NEOPORPHYRA HAITANENSIS* AND *NEOPYROPIA YEZOENSIS* UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE BASED ON MAXENT PREDICTION AND PHYLOGEOGRAPHIC PROFILING

China

Challenge

The impacts of climate change on the geographic and phylogeographic distribution of macroalgae are substantial, significantly affecting their conservation and sustainable utilization.

Contribution

This study employed the MaxEnt approach to predict both present and future habitat suitability for *N. haitanensis* and *N. yezoensis*. Additionally, the phylogeographic pattern of the species was profiled based on chloroplast *rbcL* sequences. These findings would contribute to conservation and sustainable utilization of *N. haitanensis* and *N. yezoensis* under global climate change.

Citation

Wenyuan Zhou, Baoxian Li, Hui Xu, et al., Potential distribution of two economic laver species-*Neoporphyra haitanensis* and *Neopyropia yezoensis* under climate change based on MaxEnt prediction and phylogeographic profiling, *Ecological Indicators*, 2023(150),110219, ISSN 1470-160X.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110219>.

Data Uses

A total of 579 occurrence records for *N. haitanensis* and 1192 records for *N. yezoensis* were obtained from GBIF from 1950 to 2022.

Bio-ORACLE (<https://bio-oracle.org/>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open Educational resources, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Zhejiang Ocean University, China
2. Yellow Sea Fisheries Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences, China
3. Laboratory for Marine Fisheries Science and Food Production Processes, Laoshan Laboratory, China
4. Jiangsu Marine Fisheries Research Institute, China

Fig. 2. Potential distribution of the two laver species under present and future climate conditions (2050 s). *N. haitanensis* under (a) present, (b) RCP 2.6, (c) RCP 4.5, (d) RCP 8.5 in Asia, (e) present, (f) RCP 2.6, (g) RCP 4.5, (h) RCP 8.5 in the United States. *N. yezoensis* under (i) present, (j) RCP 2.6, (k) RCP 4.5, (l) RCP 8.5 in Asia, (m) present, (n) RCP 2.6, (o) RCP 4.5, (p) RCP 8.5 in the United States.

Fig. 3. Shift of the distribution of *N. haitanensis* and *N. yezoensis* in Northwest Pacific in 2050 s. *N. haitanensis* under (a) RCP 2.6, (b) RCP 4.5, (c) RCP 8.5, *N. yezoensis* under (d) RCP 2.6, (e) RCP 4.5, (f) RCP 8.5.

13.3 PREDICTING DISTRIBUTION AND RANGE DYNAMICS OF THREE THREATENED *CYPRIPEDIUM* SPECIES UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE SCENARIO IN WESTERN HIMALAYA

India

Challenge

Climate change and anthropogenic pressure have significantly contributed to the worldwide decline of biodiversity, particularly in mountain ecosystems like the Himalaya. Orchids, known for their sensitive to disturbances, may exhibit quicker responses to climate change impacts than other plant species. Given their complex biology and anthropogenic pressures on their habitat in the Himalayan region, lady's slipper orchids are considered as a highly vulnerable group within the orchid family.

Contribution

Aside from providing useful information for conservation planning and participatory management, these distribution maps will enable the discovery of previously undocumented sites.

Several policymaking agencies may benefit from the generated information, including the Department of Forestry, the Board of Biodiversity, the Board of Medicinal Plants (SMPB), and the Ministry of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change (MOEF & CC). The establishment of a Biodiversity Management Committee (BMC) could serve as a pivotal step toward the restoration of existing habitats.

Citation

Chandra, N.; Singh, G.; Rai, I.D.; Mishra, A.P.; Kazmi, M.Y.; Pandey, A.; Jalal, J.S.; Costache, R.; Almohamad, H.; Al-Mutiry, M.; et al. Predicting Distribution and Range Dynamics of Three Threatened *Cypripedium* Species under Climate Change Scenario in Western Himalaya. *Forests* 2023, 14, 633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14030633>

Data Uses

Distribution data were compiled from global sources such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF.org) and local herbaria such as the Forest Research Institute (DD), Botanical Survey of India (BSD), and Wildlife Institute of India (WII).

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Uttarakhand Space Application Centre, India
2. Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), India
3. Wildlife Institute of India, India
4. Soban Singh Jeena University, India
5. Botanical Survey of India, India
6. National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management, Romania
7. Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania
8. Qassim University, Saudi Arabia
9. Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Saudi Arabia
10. University of Tartous, Syria
11. Damascus University, Syria
12. Tishreen University, Syria

Figure 1. Study area map with decadal climatic data (Temperature, Precipitation).

14.1 PREDICTING THE GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF *ACROPORA MURICATA* IN TWO LESSER-KNOWN REEF SYSTEMS OF THE ANDAMAN SEA

Eastern Indian Ocean

Challenge

Coral reefs are experiencing deterioration worldwide due to climate and anthropogenic stressors, despite their significant contributions to marine biodiversity and essential services for humans. Understanding the extent of hard coral distribution is essential for designing conservation strategies such as Marine Protected Areas (MPA). However, the transboundary island groups of the Andaman Sea—Andaman, Nicobar and Mergui Archipelagos—are largely underexplored and undermanaged due to their remoteness and various political constraints.

Contribution

This study contributes toward designing a transboundary conservation network and developing management plans to maintain sustainable fisheries.

Citation

Anakha, M., Sreenath, K.R., Joshi, K.K. et al. Predicting the geographical distribution of *Acropora muricata* in two lesser-known reef systems of the Andaman Sea. *J Coast Conserv* 26, 81 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-022-00925-9>

Data Uses

GBIF.org (2019) GBIF Occurrence Download. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.8ytzjl>

the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) (GEBCO 2020), the Ocean color web database (Feldman and Mc Clain 2010), HYCOM (<http://hycom.org>), Globcolour (<http://globcolour.info>)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Kerala Agricultural University, India
2. Kerala University of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences, India
3. Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute, India
4. Nansen Environmental Research Centre India, India

Fig. 1 Study Area: Andaman Sea with observed *A. muricata* occurrence points

14.2 NAJAS MARINA (HYDROCHARITACEAE) IN SOUTHERN MIDDLE SIBERIA, REFINDS AFTER A CENTURY-OLD RECESS

Russia

Challenge

New findings in the southern region of the Krasnoyarsk Territory in Middle Siberia, Russia, have confirmed the presence of *N. marina*, complementing historical collections dating back over a century in the South-Minusinsk basin.

Contribution

The aim of this communication is to review the herbarium specimens of *Najas marina* s. l. from Middle Siberia (Krasnoyarsk Territory, Republic of Khakassia, Republic of Tuva), and clarify its taxonomic classification.

Citation

Efimov, D.Y., Pimenov, A.V. & Bobrov, A.A. *Najas marina* (Hydrocharitaceae) in Southern Middle Siberia, Refinds after a Century-Old Recess. *Inland Water Biol* 16, 1178–1184 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1995082923060081>

Data Uses

iNaturalist, contributors. 2021. iNaturalist Research-grade Observations. iNaturalist.org. <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4046279375>. Cited September 3, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.15468/ab3s5x>

iNaturalist, contributors. 2022. iNaturalist Research-grade Observations. iNaturalist.org. <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3873395966>. Cited September 3, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.15468/ab3s5x>

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Papanin Institute for Biology of Inland Waters Russian Academy of Sciences, Russia
2. Krasnoyarsk Regional Museum, Russia
3. Tyumen State University, Russia

Fig. 1. Data collections plot: (a) historical voucher specimen of *Najas marina* s. str. collected in the south of the Krasnoyarsk Territory (KRM); (b) living plant in Lake Maloe Kyzyl'skoe (photo by D. Efimov, July 2021); (c) marginal teeth (the arrow) on leaf sheaths on historical specimen from Lake Kyzyl'skoe; (d) marginal teeth (the arrow) on leaf sheaths on recent specimen from Lake Maloe Kyzyl'skoe (scale bar 5 mm); (e) localities of *Najas marina* s. str. with markers of initial identification in the Krasnoyarsk Territory and adjacent area (IBW, IRKU, KRM, KUZ, MW); (f) distribution of localities of *Najas marina* s. str. in relief;

15.1 DYNAMIC FORAGING STRATEGY ADAPTATION TO HETEROGENEOUS ENVIRONMENTS CONTRIBUTES TO SOCIAL AGGREGATION IN SNUB-NOSED MONKEYS

China

Challenge

The social structures of animals undergo significant influence from environmental patterns of competition and cooperation. In folivorous colobine primates, prevailing theories suggest that larger group sizes should be favored in rainforests with a year-round abundance of food, thereby reducing feeding competition. Yet, paradoxically, larger groups are frequently found in high-altitude or high-latitude montane ecosystems characterized by a seasonal scarcity of leaves. This contradiction is posited to arise from cooperative benefits in heterogeneous environments.

Contribution

The findings of this paper shed light on how various factors have shaped social evolution via multiple pathways in a colobine clade of primates, offering insights into the complex and diverse social structures observed across a broad range of animal taxa.

Citation

Lan Zhao, Sheng-Nan Ji, Xiao-Bing Du, et al. Dynamic foraging strategy adaptation to heterogeneous environments contributes to social aggregation in snub-nosed monkeys. *Zoological Research*, 2024, 45(1): 39-54. doi: 10.24272/j.issn.2095-8137.2023.047

Data Uses

occurrence data from the GBIF
bioclimatic data from WorldClim

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Northwest University, China
2. Chengdu Institute of Biology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
3. Chinese Research Academy of Environmental Sciences, China

Figure 1 Distribution of colobines and geographical location of study area
A: Distribution of colobines. Map displays exponentially weighted difference in Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) between adjacent pixels, indicating spatial heterogeneity of habitats, i.e., habitat contrast. Distribution coordinates are scaled by average group size or population size and colored by elevation. B: Geographical location of study sites. C: Mountainous terrain around study area. D: GPS coordinates and sample sites in this study. Illustrations of monkeys: copyright 2013, Stephen D. Nash/IUCN SSC Primate Specialist Group. All illustrations are used with permission.

15.2 ASSESSING HIGH CONSERVATION VALUE AREAS FOR RARE, ENDEMIC AND THREATENED (RET) SPECIES: A STUDY IN HIGH ALTITUDE CHANGTHANG LANDSCAPE OF INDIA

India

Challenge

The Forest Stewardship Council introduced the concept of High Conservation Values (HCVs) as a criteria in the forest certification process in order to promote sustainable forest management. Comprising six major components or values, HCVs, particularly components one and two, address the habitat for viable populations of “rare, endemic and threatened (RET) species” using the IUCN Red List category and other national / regional / local lists. However, a consistent robust methodology for identification of these areas, does not exist.

Contribution

The proposed methodology addresses the urgent need for a holistic and robust set of techniques to implement the HCV toolkit. This is crucial for identifying and mapping HCVs for RET species at the landscape level and can be easily adapted to and adopted at the national, regional, state or local level in India. These methods offer an efficient and reliable approach for the application of the HCV concept, elsewhere in the world.

Citation

Meheeb Sahana, Gopala Areendran, Akhil Sivadas, et al. Assessing high conservation value areas for rare, endemic and threatened (RET) species: A study in high altitude Changthang landscape of India, *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 2023,73, 126406, ISSN 1617-1381.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2023.126406>

Data Uses

GBIF, eBird

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Indira Gandhi Conservation Monitoring Centre (IGCMC), India
2. University of Manchester, United Kingdom
3. Indira Gandhi Conservation Monitoring Centre (IGCMC), India
4. National Conservation program, India
5. National Tiger Conservation Authority (NTCA), India

Fig. 1. Location of Changthang landscape in the Ladakh Trans Himalayan Region of India.

Fig. 2. Locations of secondary and primary occurrence data for 32 selected flora, 10 fauna and 8 avifauna RET species in Changthang landscape.

15.3 ECOREGIONAL AND PHYTOGEOGRAPHICAL INSIGHTS INTO THE DISTRIBUTION OF *TULIPA* IN THE ‘NATURE IMPERILED’ AREA OF CENTRAL ASIA FOR EFFECTIVE CONSERVATION

Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Challenge

The genus *Tulipa L.* (Liliaceae) comprises roughly 150 species. Despite Central Asia being the main center of its diversity, with around 66 species, detailed mapping of their distribution remains limited, and research on their ecoregional and phytogeographical dispersion is insufficient.

Contribution

This study aimed to map and analyze the distribution patterns of *Tulipa* across the Central Asian ecoregions and phytogeographical regions to identify potential hotspots for effective conservation efforts. The findings offer valuable insights into the distribution of *Tulipa* and enable feasible recommendations and suggestions for their conservation.

Citation

Asatulloev, T.; Dekhkonov, D.; Yusupov, Z.; Tojiboeva, U.; Cai, L.; Tojibaev, K.; Sun, W. Ecoregional and Phytogeographical Insights into the Distribution of *Tulipa* in the ‘Nature Imperiled’ Area of Central Asia for Effective Conservation. *Diversity* 2023, 15, 1195. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15121195>

Data Uses

GBIF.org. (01 June 2023) GBIF Occurrence Download; GBIF: København, Denmark, 2023.

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open source software

Affiliations

1. Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China;
2. Namangan State University, Uzbekistan
3. University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
4. Institute of Botany, Academy of Sciences, Uzbekistan

Figure 1. Ecoregions of Central Asia (above) [2], and ecoregions with asterisks hold at least one species. Species richness map of species of *Tulipa* (below) in these ecoregions (additionally, Table S1 provides information about each ecoregion and its corresponding species).

16.1 DO OUR PROJECT DELIMITATIONS DISPLAY A CONTINUED LEGACY OF COLONIALISM? TOWARDS AN INDEPENDANT FLORA OF CAMBODIA

Cambodia

Challenge

Cambodia is a developing country and a biodiversity hotspot. Regrettably, Cambodia's tragic and violent history has severely hindered the understanding of its biodiversity, particularly its plant life.

Contribution

The ultimate objective is to compile a comprehensive flora of Cambodia. In the short term, the project aims to provide an open and curated checklist of vascular plants of Cambodia, available in multiple languages, including Khmer and freely available following Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR) principles. This endeavor seeks to empower both Khmer botanists and the broader local community, enabling them to reclaim and cherish their intrinsic knowledge of native plants.

Citation

Ung V (2023) Do our Project Delimitations Display a Continued Legacy of Colonialism? Towards an independant Flora of Cambodia. DOI: 10.3897/biss.7.110680

Data Uses

GBIF

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

CNRS-MNHN-SU-EPHE-UA, France

Figure 1. [doi](#)
 Map showing the continental shelf, island area and Australian phytogeographic subregions (Ebach et al. 2015) that species were coded to in the SSCZ vascular plant checklist. MAS, Mainland Asia; Sum, Sumatra; Bor, Borneo; Jav, Java; Phi, Philippines; Sul, Sulawesi; LSI, Lesser Sunda Islands; Mik, Maluku Islands; NGu, New Guinea; AKP, Kimberley Plateau; AAL, Arnhem Land; ACY, Cape York Peninsula; AAP, Atherton Plateau; AGS, Great Sandy Desert Interzone; ACD, Central Desert; ACQ, Central Queensland; AEQ, Eastern Queensland; AWD, Western Desert; AED, Eastern Desert; ASe, Southeastern; ASw, Southwestern; ASI, Southwest Interzone; AHa, Hampton; ANu, Nullarbor; AEP, Eyre Peninsula; AAd, Adelaide; AVi, Victoria; ATa, Tasmania.

16.2 GLOBAL ACCESS TO NOMENCLATURAL BOTANICAL RESOURCES: EVALUATING OPEN ACCESS AVAILABILITY

South Asia and Global

Challenge

A decade has passed since electronic publication was adopted by the botanical community, with the expectation that it would make plant diversity information more openly and widely accessible. However, despite initial acceptance, it is evident that electronic publication has not significantly improved the availability of this information in an open way. The term 'undiscoverable' does not mean that this information is not available in electronic space, but rather the lack of identifiers means that searching for, retrieving and ultimately relocating such resources is time-consuming and can be costly.

Contribution

This paper outlines below some specific recommendations for actions that could enhance accessibility to resources, as well as suggestions for future research that could further analyse the situation.

Citation

Nicolson N, Trekels M, J. Groom Q, et al. Global access to nomenclatural botanical resources: Evaluating open access availability. *Plants People Planet*, 2023,5(6):899-907.

DOI:10.1002/ppp3.10438

Data Uses

To assess the availability of type specimen metadata through open access, the study used the GBIF to download a DarwinCore dataset of all vascular plant occurrences based on preserved specimens with a type status (Gbif.Org, 2022).

the International Plant Names Index (IPNI), the World Checklist of Vascular Plants (WCVP)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data

Affiliations

1. Royal Botanic Gardens, UK
2. Meise Botanic Garden, Belgium
3. Natural History Museum, UK

(a) Proportion of all IPNI nomenclatural acts (2012-2021) which are non-discoverable

(b) Ratio of open:closed access of all IPNI nomenclatural acts (2012-2021)

FIGURE 4 (a) Proportion of International Plant Names Index (IPNI) nomenclatural act records that are non-discoverable and (b) their ratio of open to closed access by World Geographic Scheme for Recording Plant Distributions (WGSRPD) level 2.

17.1 AVIAN SPECIES SURVEY WITH CITIZEN-SCIENCE DATA IN JANGHANG WETLAND, GOYANG, REPUBLIC OF KOREA

Korea

Challenge

The Janghang Wetland, situated in the Han River estuary, holds international significance. This estuarine wetland teeming with a stretch of *Salix koreensis* (Korean willows), rarely seen in other brackish water zones of Korea. The *Salix koreensis* community has not only a symbiotic relationship with benthos, including *Chiromantes dehaani*, *Sesarmops intermedius* and *Ilyoplax deschampsii*, which are indicator species of a blackish water zone, but also plays a role in regulating temperature of the urban area, decreasing carbon and protecting the margins of the river. Moreover, it serves as an important stopover site for more than 30,000 birds each year, providing habitat and food for winter visitors.

Contribution

This work aimed to conduct an inventory of the waterbirds in the inner border area of Goyang in ROK, focused on the Janghang Wetland.

Citation

Choi H-A, Lee E, Kim E, Jung I, Han D (2023) Avian species survey with citizen-science data in Janghang Wetland, Goyang, Republic of Korea. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 11: e105580. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.11.e105580>

Data Uses

<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/adaaa817-289b-4c23-9cc1-097195944cdc>

the IOC World Bird List version 13.1 (Gill et al. 2023)

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, Open Educational resources, Citizen Science

Affiliations

1. Hanns Seidel Foundation Korea, Republic of Korea
2. Korea University, Republic of Korea
3. PGA Eco and Bio Diversity Institute, Republic of Korea
4. Kongju National University, Republic of Korea

Figure 1. [doi](#)

The survey area, Janghang Wetland (Sourced by authors' compilation, based on the map of Janghang Wetland by Goyang City).

Figure 2. [doi](#)

The survey points (A-E), sensor camera point (B) and closed-circuit television camera point (C) (Sourced by authors' compilation, based on Google Earth).

17.2 INCREASING BIODIVERSITY KNOWLEDGE THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA: A CASE STUDY FROM TROPICAL BANGLADESH

Bangladesh

Challenge

Citizen science programs are gaining popularity among naturalists; however, they still exhibit significant taxonomic and geographical biases. Yet, with the explosive popularity of social media and the near-ubiquitous availability of smartphones, many individuals share wildlife photographs on these platforms.

Contribution

In this context, the study illustrates the potential of harvesting these data to enhance our biodiversity understanding using Bangladesh, a tropical biodiverse country, as a case study. Addressing the global biodiversity data shortfall, a key research priority now is the development of mechanisms for extracting and interpreting social media biodiversity data.

Citation

Shawan Chowdhury, Upama Aich, Md Rokonzaman, et al., Increasing biodiversity knowledge through social media: A case study from tropical Bangladesh, *BioScience*, Volume 73, Issue 6, June 2023, Pages 453–459, <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biad042>

Data Uses

712 species from GBIF
Facebook

Open Sciences

Open scientific publications, Open research data, open source software

Affiliations

1. University of Queensland, Australia
2. Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Germany
3. Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research—UFZ, Germany
4. German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research, Germany
5. Monash University, Australia
6. University of Dhaka, Bangladesh
7. Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
8. University of Florida, United States

Figure 1. Distribution (a) and taxonomic group-wise number (b) of geospatial records for Bangladeshi animals using records from both Facebook (F) and GBIF (G). The photographs are some species for which we only obtained distribution records from Facebook. The source of these photographs are the following: Ms Saira Jureali (*Morsia pentadactyla*), Gerard Chatter (Euploea cramerii), Charles J Sharp (*Gaviola gangetica*), Jason Thompson (*Tringa guttifer*), and Shawan Chowdhury (*Kalima inachus*).

Figure 2. The difference in extent of occurrence (EOO, in square kilometers) for Bangladeshi animals using geospatial records from Facebook and GBIF. The dashed line indicates where the EOO estimates from Facebook and GBIF were identical.

Index of the Guide

NO.	Title	Area	SDGs	Open Science	Page
1.1	Diversity of wild edible fruits in the agroforestry area of Cigalontang Village, Tasikmalaya, Indonesia	Indonesia	1	OSP; ORD	6
1.2	Crop wild relatives in Lebanon: mapping the distribution of Poaceae and Fabaceae priority taxa for conservation planning	Lebanon	1	OSP; ORD; OSS	7
2.1	Dulong People's Traditional Knowledge of <i>Caryota obtusa</i> (Arecaceae): a Potential Starch Plant with Emphasis on Its Starch Properties and Distribution Prediction	China	2	OSP; ORD; OSS	8
2.2	Smart farming: modeling distribution of <i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i> as a leaf blight-causing bacteria in rice plants	Indonesia	2	OSP; ORD; OSS	9
2.3	Ethnobotany of medicinal plants in the Dayak Linoh Tribe in Sintang District, Indonesia	Indonesia	2	OSP; ORD	10
3.1	Potential individual and interactive effects of climate and land-cover changes on bats and implications for conservation planning: a case study in Vietnam	Vietnam	3	OSP; ORD; OSS	11
3.2	Mapping Potential Regions of Human Interaction with Acuminate Horseshoe Bats (<i>Rhinolophus acuminatus</i>) in Thailand	Thailand	3	OSP; ORD; OSS	12
4.1	Identifying high snakebite risk area under climate change for community education and antivenom distribution	Iran	4	OSP; ORD; OSS; OER; CS	13
4.2	Conserving Potential and Endangered Species of <i>Pericopsis mooniana</i> Thwaites in Indonesia	Indonesia	4	OSP; ORD; OER	14
4.3	Status of ornithological works from the state of Chhattisgarh, India, and conservation implications: A review	India	4	ORD; OER; OSS	15
5.1	Ethnobotany of food plants used by Minangkabau Community in Lima Puluh Kota District, West Sumatra, Indonesia	Indonesia	5	OSP; ORD	16
5.2	Smoke and Mirrors: The Global Trade in Fern (<i>Lygodium circinnatum</i>) Fiber Basketry	Indonesia	5	OSP; ORD	17
6.1	Date palm cultivation: A review of soil and environmental conditions and future challenges	Saudi Arabia	6	OSP; ORD	18
7.1	Biotechnological interventions in bamboo plants	China, India	7	OSP; ORD; OSS	19
8.1	Progress on Geographical Distribution, Driving Factors and Ecological Functions of Nepalese Alder	China, India	8	OSP; ORD; OSS	20
9.1	Towards a bionic IoT: Environmental monitoring using smartphone interrogated plant sensors	Asia	9	OSP; ORD	21
9.2	Reducing global land-use pressures with seaweed farming	Indonesia	9	OSP; ORD	22
9.3	Ecology with artificial intelligence and machine learning in Asia: A historical perspective and emerging trends	China, Korea, Japan, India, and Iran.	9	OSP; ORD; OSS	23
10.1	The colonial legacy of herbaria	Asia	10	OSP; ORD; OSS	24
10.2	Unevenly distributed biological invasion costs among origin and recipient regions	Asia	10	OSP; ORD	25
11.1	Human activity and climate change accelerate the extinction risk to non-human primates in China	China	11	OSP; ORD; OSS	26

NO.	Title	Area	SDGs	Open Science	Page
11.2	Evaluating the Urban-Rural Differences in the Environmental Factors Affecting Amphibian Roadkill	China	11	OSP; ORD; OSS	27
11.3	Are the same factors determining biodiversity in cities across different regions? Comparing drivers of urban bird richness patterns in Southern Asia vs. Western Europe	Southern Asia and Western Europe	11	OSP; ORD	28
12.1	Species availability and socio-economics drive prosecutions for regional mammal and bird poaching across China, 2014–2020	China	12	OSP; ORD; OSS	29
12.2	Ecology and conservation of threatened medicinal plants in the Trans-Himalayan region of Nanda Devi Biosphere Reserve, Western Himalaya	India	12	OSP; ORD; OSS	30
13.1	Distribution change and protected area planning of <i>Tilia amurensis</i> in China: A study of integrating the climate change and present habitat landscape pattern	China	13	OSP; ORD; OSS	31
13.2	Potential distribution of two economic laver species- <i>Neoporphyra haitanensis</i> and <i>Neopyropia yezoensis</i> under climate change based on MaxEnt prediction and phylogeographic profiling	China	13	OSP; ORD; OER; OSS	32
13.3	Predicting Distribution and Range Dynamics of Three Threatened <i>Cypripedium</i> Species under Climate Change Scenario in Western Himalaya	India	13	OSP; ORD	33
14.1	Predicting the geographical distribution of <i>Acropora muricata</i> in two lesser-known reef systems of the Andaman Sea	India	14	OSP; ORD; OSS	34
14.2	<i>Najas marina</i> (Hydrocharitaceae) in Southern Middle Siberia, Refinds after a Century-Old Recess	Russia	14	OSP; ORD	35
15.1	Dynamic foraging strategy adaptation to heterogeneous environments contributes to social aggregation in snub-nosed monkeys	China	15	OSP; ORD; OSS	36
15.2	Assessing high conservation value areas for rare, endemic and threatened (RET) species: A study in high altitude Changthang landscape of India	India	15	OSP; ORD	37
15.3	Ecoregional and Phytogeographical Insights into the Distribution of Tulipa in the 'Nature Imperiled' Area of Central Asia for Effective Conservation	Kazakhstan; Uzbekistan; Turkmenistan; Kyrgyzstan; Tajikistan	15	OSP; ORD; OSS	38
16.1	Do our Project Delimitations Display a Continued Legacy of Colonialism? Towards an independant Flora of Cambodia	Cambodia	16	OSP; ORD	39
16.2	Global access to nomenclatural botanical resources: Evaluating open access availability	south Asia and Global	16	OSP; ORD	40
17.1	Avian species survey with citizen-science data in Janghang Wetland, Goyang, Republic of Korea	Korea	17	OSP; ORD; OER; CS	41
17.2	Increasing biodiversity knowledge through social media: A case study from tropical Bangladesh	Bangladesh	17	OSP; ORD; OSS; CS	42

Note: The abbreviations in open science: OSP: Open Scientific Publication; ORD: Open Research Data; OSS: Open Source Software; OER: Open Educational Resources; CS: Citizen Science.

